

THE QUESTION OF ACTIVATED OXALIC ACID

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The active agent immediately responsible for the reduction of HgCl_2 by permanganate treated oxalic acid appears to be the unstable acid $\text{HMn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$. The latter decomposes spontaneously producing CO_2 -ions

In the presence of free oxalic acid only, the reducing activity ceases immediately upon the disappearance of $\text{HMn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$. There is no evidence of any activated form of oxalic acid persisting in aqueous solution. Mixtures of KMnO_4 and anhydrous oxalic acid do not reduce mercuric chloride in acetone. Neutral $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ slowly decolourises KMnO_4 at concentrations of the latter below $10^{-4}N$ leaving optically clear solutions. The latter under nitrogen retain the power of reducing HgCl_2 for periods up to 24 hours at room temperature in the dark. The retention of activity is due to the formation of stable $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ under these conditions. KMnO_4 added to neutral oxalate in concentrations between 10^{-3} and $10^{-4}N$ shows a direct relationship between the amount added and the yield of calomel.

The half-ion CO_2' (or $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4''$) initiates a chain mechanism. They are straight chains of great length not involving regeneration of trivalent manganese as part of the mechanism. The formation of H_2O_2 and the slow catalytic oxidation of oxalic acid in the presence of Mn^{2+} are complicated reactions not necessarily involving the assumption of an activated form of oxalic acid. The inhibitory action of oxygen affects the chain process and not any of the permanganate reduction products initiating the reaction. Traces of Mn^{2+} ions retard the iodine-oxalate reaction both in air and under nitrogen using oxalate concentrations over $N/10$. There is no evidence of any action of atmospheric oxygen on CO_2' -ions producing a peroxide of carbon.

In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 429) we drew attention to the possibility of correlating the mechanism of the after-effect in the oxalate-iodine reaction with the so-called activation of oxalic acid brought about by the addition of small quantities of oxidising agents such as potassium permanganate in aqueous solution.

We came to the conclusion, however, that the mechanism of these two reactions is quite distinct, since end solutions in the iodine-oxalate reactions, when all the iodine had been used up photochemically, were not found to have the reducing effect on mercuric chloride characteristic of permanganate treated oxalate. This conclusion was based on the assumed existence of an "activated" form of oxalic acid of abnormally long life surviving at the end of the latter reaction. It may be stated at once that we now find no evidence for the existence of such an activated form, so that the possibility of similar reaction mechanisms can no longer be excluded.

Attention to the permanganate-oxalic acid reaction was first drawn by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 690) who regarded it as an example of induced oxidation. The idea of the formation of a more active energy-richer form of oxalic acid appears to have originated with Oberhauser and Hensing (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 521) who thought they had obtained experimental evidence of its persistence in solution for long periods (up to 24 hours at room temperature) after the permanganate had been used up in the presence of a large excess of oxalic acid. This evidence consisted mainly of the fact that hydrogen peroxide is formed when such solutions continue to be exposed to air or oxygen. The activated oxalic acid could react equally well with mercuric chloride or oxygen, or any other suitable acceptor:

The above conclusions were shown to be erroneous by Wieland and Zilg (*Annalen*, 1937, 580, 257) who obtained the same quantities of hydrogen peroxide by bubbling oxygen through solutions containing the same concentrations of oxalic acid to which had been added Mn^{2+} ions equivalent in amount to the permanganate used in previous experiments.

Oberhauser and Schormüller (*ibid.*, 1929, 470, 111) furthermore stated that an aqueous medium was not necessary for the activation. They claimed to have obtained the activated acid using acetone as solvent.

We have carefully repeated this work in a number of experiments using the method mentioned later, and have been wholly unable to confirm their results.

Acetone was purified by distillation over solid potassium permanganate and redistilled over calcium chloride. Acetone solutions of pure anhydrous oxalic acid and of mercuric chloride were mixed and freed from oxygen by passing nitrogen slowly through the mixture for some hours and the acetone solution of potassium permanganate added in the sealed vessel in the dark. A slight brownish precipitate was obtained which turned white overnight. Analysis proved it to be manganese oxalate, MnC_2O_4 , and there was no trace of calomel. No reduction was obtained by varying the order in which the reactants were mixed. Furthermore, we have been unable to confirm the statement of Oberhauser and Schormüller (*loc. cit.*) that after removal of all the manganese by the usual analytical means, the existence of the activated form of oxalic acid could still be established in the filtrate. In these particular experiments, using potassium permanganate as inductor, we have never been able to observe the reduction of mercuric chloride unless manganese is present in some form or other.

Oberhauser subsequently abandoned the idea of the existence of oxalic acid in two tautomeric forms, one more reactive than the other, and suggested that the activated form is a labile intermediate state between the normal homopolar molecule and complete ionisation, containing excited electron-pairs forming the hydrogen-oxygen linkages.

Wieland and Zilg (*loc. cit.*) were able to disprove the assertion that an active form of oxalic acid was stable over long periods, by performing the experiments under nitrogen. Mercuric chloride was added to permanganate-treated oxalic acid at definite intervals after decolourisation. The latter was found to have almost completely lost its activity after two minutes. These authors have considered that the activation of the oxalic acid molecule is brought about by absorption of energy derived from the primary oxidation process; the hydrogen linkage is "loosened" and so the hydrogen reacts more readily with a suitable acceptor and the acid residue conveys part of the liberated energy to further oxalic acid molecules, thereby initiating a kind of energy chain in solution.

In the course of this investigation we noticed that by adding small quantities of potassium permanganate to neutral potassium oxalate solution, the colour gradually disappeared without the visible appearance of manganese dioxide below certain limits of concentration of the former, and the clear colourless solution so obtained strongly reduced mercuric chloride in the dark under nitrogen. Examination in the ultra-microscope failed to reveal colloidal particles of hydrated manganese dioxide. In the following experiments the concentration of potassium permanganate in the reacting solution was usually at a maximum of about $4 \times 10^{-3}N$. When larger quantities of potassium permanganate are employed, the brown colour of hydrated manganese dioxide makes its appearance. If the reaction consists in the oxidation of free oxalic acid derived from the slight hydrolysis of potassium oxalate, there should be a slight appearance of alkalinity, resulting in the formation of $Mn(OH)_2$ above a certain small limiting concentration of permanganate. It is noteworthy that Fox, Swinehart and Garrett (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1779) have determined the solubility of the latter to be 0.4×10^{-8} moles per litre, which is of the same order as the concentration of potassium permanganate used in these experiments.

In all experiments conductivity water was used and there was no loss of potassium permanganate over many months, showing the absence of organic reducing impurities.

The reactions using neutral oxalate in place of the free acid, in common with the latter, are inhibited by atmospheric oxygen. After admixture with mercuric chloride, it becomes susceptible to light (*Eder reaction*) so that all experiments had to be carried out rigorously in the dark and under nitrogen.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experiments were carried out in pyrex glass flasks fitted with a sealed-on bulb containing the requisite quantity of mercuric chloride and another side-tube containing either potassium permanganate solution, solid potassium permanganate, or MnO_2 . Nitrogen was bubbled for some hours through the oxalate solution and the whole sealed off. Manganese was then added and subsequently mercuric chloride at stated intervals. The mixtures were found to be highly susceptible to traces of alkali from soda glass. When the solutions of potassium oxalate underwent a preliminary boiling in a current of nitrogen to expel air and the usual procedure followed after cooling, they reacted immediately on admixture with mercuric chloride in the dark. No reactivity was found in blank experiments using pyrex vessels, taking care not to give too much preliminary heating. The following experiments represent some of the results obtained, using both the free acid and neutral potassium oxalate.

Reaction between "Activated" Free Oxalic Acid and Mercuric Chloride

The reacting solutions were in all cases brought up to 50 c.c. at room temperature. At the end of the times stated, the flasks were cut open and the mercurous chloride filtered off, dried and weighed.

Expt. 1.— $N-H_2C_2O_4$ (25 c.c.) was treated with solid $KMnO_4$ (0.01 g.). When all the purple colour had disappeared and only a yellowish brown solution remained, 20 c.c. of 5% mercuric chloride solution were added. There was a quantitative reduction in 3 hours. The above experiment was repeated. When the yellowish brown solution had been obtained, air was admitted and mercuric chloride then added. The reduction to calomel was now very largely diminished, although the brown colour took longer to disappear.

Expt. 2.—About 0.01 g. of solid potassium permanganate was added to 20 c.c. of $N-H_2C_2O_4$ and $HgCl_2$ added as soon as possible after the yellowish brown colour was no longer visible. No reduction whatever to mercurous chloride took place even after standing 24 hours in the dark. The estimated interval after decolourisation was 1 to 2 minutes.

These experiments confirm the results of Wieland and Zilg (*loc. cit.*) and show that there is no justification for assuming the continued existence of an activated form of oxalic acid after the inductor is used up. So long as these solutions were visibly coloured brown and mercuric chloride added there was quantitative reduction, but with the means at our disposal it was impossible to say at what precise instant the brown substance disappeared. This substance is unstable and disappears spontaneously at room temperature within a few minutes. On warming the sealed flask gently the solution suddenly becomes colourless and is suffused with minute bubbles of CO_2 . It is thus a higher unstable compound, probably of tervalent manganese and will be discussed later. With potassium oxalate it forms the pink complex salt $K_3Mn(C_2O_4)_3$. This was easily shown by adding excess of potassium oxalate to the brown solution from a side-bulb, when the pink colour immediately appeared. In our experiments the latter remained for 24 hours in the dark and reduced mercuric chloride quantitatively. It decolourises immediately in sunlight and is undoubtedly $K_3Mn(C_2O_4)_3$. The stability is greater, the greater the excess of acidified potassium oxalate.

It thus appears from these experiments that the primary oxidation of oxalic acid by potassium permanganate is not an essential part of the process of "activation".

It has sometimes been stated that the reactant immediately responsible is the complex salt. That this is not the case can be shown by substituting solid hydrated $Mn(O)_2$ for potassium permanganate. The former was prepared by the electrolysis of $MnSO_4$ solution, as the specimens prepared by the usual methods of reducing potassium permanganate were invariably found to contain potassium. On adding small fragments of about 0.01 g. of hydrated $Mn(O)_2$ from a side-tube the same brown coloured solution was obtained, with the same reducing effect on mercuric chloride.

It may be mentioned that a highly reactive pink substance may be obtained by treating pure concentrated oxalic acid with the solid $Mn(O)_2$ hydrate. A vigorous reaction takes place with evolution of heat and CO_2 . If filtered rapidly a red solution is obtained stable for some time in the presence of excess concentrated oxalic acid. On dilution it gives a brown substance containing much hydrogen peroxide, which becomes colourless with further evolution of CO_2 . The pink solution readily reduces mercuric chloride in air and appears to be either a *peroxalate* of manganese, or free mangani-oxalic acid $H_2Mn(C_2O_4)_2$.

In all the above experiments, substitution of Mn^{II} ions for $KMnO_4$ gave negative results with mercuric chloride under nitrogen. We have thus reason to believe that the reaction is initiated, not by the energy liberated in the primary oxidation (dehydrogenation) of oxalic acid, but by Mn^{III} ions or some complex capable of producing them. An overall equation at the manganic stage may be written as

As previously stated, experiments were carried out using neutral solutions of potassium oxalate to which small quantities of $KMnO_4$ had been added up to a limit not exceeding $10^{-5}N$. The pink colour of the permanganate took some time to disappear at room temperature leaving an optically clear solution.

TABLE I

HgCl ₂ added after addition of $KMnO_4$ at intervals of	Mercurous chloride formed		
	Expt. 3, at 26°.	Expt. 4 at 26°.	Expt. 5 at 34°.
0 hour	0.7564 g.	0.8678 g.	0.8856 g.
1	0.3032	0.8712	0.8774
2	0.1968	0.5478	0.6582
3	—	—	0.3046
4	0.0062	0.3432	—
6	—	—	0.0748
8	—	0.0132	—
12	0.0036	0.0056	0.0048
16	0.0028	0.0032	—
24	A faint opalescence	Opalescence	Opalescence

* Simultaneous addition of $KMnO_4$ and $HgCl_2$ to potassium oxalate.

Reaction between $K_2C_2O_4$, $KMnO_4$ and $HgCl_2$

Expt. 3.— $N-K_2C_2O_4$ (25 c.c.), 5% $HgCl_2$ (20 c.c.), $N/209-KMnO_4$ (0.4 c.c.) and water (4.6 c.c.) were taken and the reaction allowed to proceed for 1 hour at 26°. Nitrogen was passed through oxalate solution, and after the vessel had been sealed off, $KMnO_4$ was added from a side-bulb. $HgCl_2$ was then added at various intervals after the addition of $KMnO_4$ as shown in Table I. The mixture was kept in the dark for 1 hour and Hg_2Cl_2 filtered off and weighed.

Expt. 4.—*Expt. 3* was repeated under the same conditions, but the reaction was allowed to proceed for 24 hours at 26° (Table I).

When the above experiments were repeated in presence of air, there was practically no reduction even after 24 hours' standing in the dark.

Expt. 5.—Experiment 4 was repeated using further recrystallised reagents. Temperature of the experiment was 34° (Table I). This result has been shown in Fig. 1.

Expt. 6.— $N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ (25 c.c.), 5% HgCl_2 (20 c.c.) and water (4.6 c.c.) were mixed together under nitrogen with varying amounts of potassium permanganate and the reaction allowed to proceed for 24 hours at 34° (see Fig. 2).

TABLE II

Conc. of $\text{KMnO}_4(N)$	... 4×10^{-3}	4×10^{-4}	4×10^{-5}	4×10^{-6}
Hg_2Cl_2 (g.)	... 0.8674	0.6594	0.2718	0.0236

These experiments show that at the higher concentrations of KMnO_4 employed the reaction takes many hours to complete in spite of the fact that some free oxalic acid must be liberated by the addition of HgCl_2 solution. When the permanganate has partly disappeared after some hours and is thus present in very low concentrations on addition of mercuric chloride, a comparison of Table I (*Expt. 3* and *4*) shows that the reaction has now been completed within 1 hour. No further increase in weight of precipitated calomel took place after one week in the dark. Blank experiments, taking the precautions already mentioned, showed no reaction between potassium oxalate and mercuric chloride.

The extent of the reactions in *Expt. 5* is shown in Fig. 1. The course is continuous from the highest concentration of KMnO_4 employed down to the vanishingly small concentrations, colourless to the eye. In *Expt. 6* the permanganate solutions added at the lower concentrations were quite colourless. Fig. 2 shows that there is a direct proportionality between the amount of KMnO_4 added and the amount of HgCl_2 reduced.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

When potassium permanganate is reduced by acidified oxalate solution, a series of colour changes takes place before complete decolourisation corresponding to successive reduction of the MnO_4' ion to colourless Mn^{II} ion.

The foregoing experiments using oxalic acid and either $KMnO_4$ or MnO_2 as oxidising agent show that the active agent, which brings about reduction, is the brown substance appearing for a short time immediately prior to decolourisation. This alone disposes of Wieland's theory that the reaction depends upon the energy liberated in the primary oxidation of oxalic acid molecules by potassium permanganate. Even when pure oxalic acid and solid MnO_2 are used the same brown solution makes its appearance so that the reaction only goes partly at least in the direction:—

or

(Manganese dioxide is a complex substance, the formula of which might be more appropriately written $MnO \cdot MnO_2$ or $3 \cdot Mn(O) \cdot Mn_2O_7$. *cf.*, Spring and Lucion, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1890, *iii*, 3, 4)

There is reason to believe that the active brown substance is derived from mangan-oxalic acid as follows:—

(Cherry red). (Brown).

Previous workers on the Eder reaction have shown that it possesses a chain mechanism with a high quantum yield (Roseveare, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2619) and the nature of the dark chemically induced reaction also points to a chain mechanism. The chains must originate from active CO_2' (or C_2O_4'')* ions produced as above (ii); the same ion has been postulated as one of the chain carriers in the iodine-oxalate reaction and its accompanying after-effect (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 429). Launer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2597 *et seq.*), who has already proposed a mechanism depending upon the presence of this ion, claims to have identified the ion $Mn(C_2O_4)_2'$ present as follows:—

We prefer to think, however, that the cherry red colour is due to the complex potassium salt formed as already described.

According to Launer (*loc. cit.*) an aqueous solution of $KMnO_4$ always contains in equilibrium MnO_4' , Mn^{VI} , Mn^{VII} and Mn^{II} ions.

There is little or no reaction between $Mn(O)_4''$ and $C_2(O)_4''$ in the absence of Mn^{VI} . The reactions which take place are as follows:—

Applying this scheme to the foregoing experiments with neutral oxalate it is evident that reactions (v) and (vii) must be instantaneous on account of the large excess of C_2O_4'' ions present and

* In discussing these reactions the active ion may be written either as CO_2' or C_2O_4'' , since there is no possibility of distinguishing between them.

(vi) and (viii) must be negligible. Since KMnO_4 disappears very slowly, the rapid equilibrium in (ii) cannot thus be a governing factor in our experiments.

We suggest that the primary reaction takes place between KMnO_4 and free oxalic acid derived from slight hydrolysis of $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, that mangani-oxalic acid is formed as a product of the reduction and that it is instantly stabilised in the presence of excess of $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ as $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$. The equilibrium

moves to the right.

Experiments of the type 3 and 6 reveal two principal characteristics, *viz.*, (a) the retention by the KMnO_4 - $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ mixture of its reducing power on HgCl_2 for periods up to 24 hours at room temperature and (b) the reaction with mercuric chloride takes several hours to complete at the maximum concentration of KMnO_4 taken.

The slowness of (a) must be due to the slow breaking down of $\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2^{2-}$ ions, which under the conditions of the experiments will be present in only slight concentration. The CO_2' ions produced will be largely removed by self-combination in the absence of a suitable reactant $\text{CO}_2' + \text{CO}_2' \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (MacMahon and Lal, *loc. cit.*).

In this connection it may be stated that the same amount of KMnO_4 (0.4 c.c. of $N/200$) added to oxalic acid ($N/10$) produces only about one tenth the amount of reduction obtained with potassium oxalate ($N/10$) after standing 24 hours under nitrogen. In the former case self-combination takes place to a large extent as shown by the instability of $\text{HMn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$.

The first effect of adding mercuric chloride, which has an acid reaction in aqueous solution, is to cause the complete conversion of KMnO_4 into $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ within a few minutes at room temperature. Hydrogen ions also have the effect, as established in other experiments, of further stabilising the latter, probably by suppressing the reaction

so that the long periods taken for the reduction of HgCl_2 to be completed are thus readily accounted for.

If every CO_2' ion produced at the final stage, $\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2^{2-} \rightarrow \text{MnC}_2\text{O}_4 + \text{CO}_2 + \text{CO}_2'$ starts a chain, the total amount of Hg_2Cl_2 precipitated will depend upon the number of chains started and hence upon the actual amount of $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ present on addition of HgCl_2 .

Experiment 6 shows that a proportionality actually exists between the amount of HgCl_2 reduced and the concentration of KMnO_4 (Fig. 2). Since there is no room in this mechanism for regeneration of Mn^{II} ions, the reaction appears to furnish a proof of the occurrence of long straight reaction chains in aqueous solution. It may be noted that experiments performed under these conditions furnish an extremely sensitive test for the presence of MnO_4' ions, down to concentrations of the order $10^{-8}N$.

While this work was in progress, a paper appeared (Cartledge, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 906) proposing the following mechanism for the actual chain process in postulating a second chain carrier Hg^+ :-

Formation of Hydrogen Peroxide and Action of Manganous Ions

The fact that hydrogen peroxide is formed when KMnO_4 is decolourised by an excess of oxalic acid has lent support to the conception of an activated form of the latter. The matter is further complicated by the inhibitory effect of oxygen in the reduction of mercuric chloride,

Experiments 1 and 4, however, show that the inhibitory effect takes place after the Mn^{IV} stage when all the permanganate has disappeared. It is thus *not* due to the competitive dehydrogenation by atmospheric oxygen of oxalic acid activated by the energy liberated in the primary oxidation as postulated by Wieland.

Experiments 1 and 4 repeated in air and in the dark showed only a faint opalescence after 4 days. The same result was observed by substituting $MnSO_4$ equivalent in amount to the permanganate (0.00005 g. $MnSO_4$). There was much H_2O_2 present after 6 months.

Expt. 7.—When, however, larger quantities of manganese sulphate were employed (0.05 to 0.5 g.) with $K_2C_2O_4$, precipitation of Hg_2Cl_2 in bulk began to take place after 48 hours in the dark, gradually increasing in rate, with the appearance of the characteristic colour of $K_2Mn(C_2O_4)_2$. This phenomenon was unaffected by the order in which the reactants were mixed.

A solution of 25 c.c. of *N*- $K_2C_2O_4$ to which 1 g. of $MnSO_4$ had been added showed no pink colour after one week; when, however, three drops of dilute sulphuric acid had been added, it appeared in a few hours in the dark and diffused light. Much hydrogen peroxide was invariably present along with the latter.

It thus appears that in the presence of oxygen and pure oxalic acid Mn^{IV} ions are converted into Mn^{III} ions and the latter are stabilised as $K_2Mn(C_2O_4)_2$ in the presence of excess of $C_2O_4^{2-}$ ions.

Richardson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 86, 450) has found that oxalic acid itself is oxidised in the presence of oxygen and light, giving H_2O_2 if the oxygen is in excess, and H_2O if in defect.

In view of Winther's finding (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1909, 7, 409; 1910, 8, 197 237) that the Eder reaction does not take place when the materials used are completely freed from iron, it might be desirable to repeat Richardson's work with oxalic acid known to be iron-free. According to Winther, 0.047 mg. $FeCl_3$ per litre is sufficient to induce the Eder reaction.

Jorissen and Reicher (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 31, 142) found that Mn^{IV} ions catalysed the oxidation of oxalic acid both in light and in the dark, that acids accelerated the oxidation and that the rate increased with the concentration of Mn^{IV} ions.

From the foregoing it appears that the formation of hydrogen peroxide is not necessarily connected with the agency of any special form of activated oxalic acid of long life. The matter is decidedly complicated and is probably connected with the still imperfectly understood mechanism of the Eder reaction. Oxalic acid oxidises in the two directions above mentioned under conditions not yet elucidated.

Catalysis of the slow oxidation by Mn^{IV} ions might be represented as follows by an overall equation, without theorising about the mechanism, since 95 % of the ionisation of *N/10*-oxalic acid at ordinary temperatures are represented by the first stage:—

The net effect would be to oxidise oxalic acid to hydrogen peroxide leaving the Mn^{IV} ions unchanged. In accordance with what has been said previously this would also account for the appearance of the pink colour in presence of excess $K_2C_2O_4$:—

In experiment 7 after about 48 hours in the dark, copious precipitation of calomel takes place along with the appearance of the pink colour and hydrogen peroxide. Under these conditions there is apparently a long induction period and after that oxygen exercises no inhibitory

effect. Something similar was found by Winther (*loc. cit.*) in the catalysis of the Eder reaction by iron salts. In the presence of a small amount of iron, oxygen retards the reaction; when the concentration of iron is high, oxygen somewhat increases the photo-rate.

Matters are complicated by high concentration of manganese ions and the number of different reactions taking place simultaneously. It has already been shown that in these mixtures trivalent manganese gradually accumulates. It can only be suggested that there arises a deficiency of oxygen in solution and the eventual high rate of chain initiation overcomes the inhibitory effect. It is to be noted that the pink colour remains stable in solution after the precipitation of calomel has ceased.

Oxygen Inhibition

When fresh hydrogen peroxide is added to the brown solution assumed to contain $\text{HMn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$, the colour is discharged. Furthermore, as noted in Expt. 4 admission of oxygen actually prolongs the life of the brown substance but largely diminishes the yield of Hg_2Cl_2 . This disposes of the possibility of the inhibitory action of oxygen being traceable to the destruction of the active manganese compound. The immediate effect appears to be rather the regeneration of trivalent manganese.

It is to be inferred, therefore, that the inhibitory effect is due to the removal of one or other of the chain-carriers. The mechanism of the process has not yet been satisfactorily explained.

Roseveare (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 870) has put forward a scheme based upon the formation in air of a permonocarbonic acid, CO_3' , which acts as follows:—

We have endeavoured to test the consequences of this when applied to the iodine-oxalate photo-reaction, in the mechanism of which the participation of C_2O_4 has been postulated.

In the first instance, it may be observed that the presence of a highly reactive peroxide of this type should tend to form hydrogen peroxide, liberate fresh iodine from potassium iodide and so produce an apparent retardation of the reaction. We find no different behaviour, in the latter, however, when carried out under nitrogen using the method already described.

Further experiments have been tried on the effect of the addition of small quantities of Mn^{++} ions to the reaction mixtures.

To solutions of 25 c.c. of $N/4$, and $N/10$ - $\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ were added 0.001 g. of MnSO_4 and 1 c.c. of $N/10$ -iodine in the dark, the mixtures then exposed to diffused light and the time of iodine decolourisation noted. Retardation of the photo-reaction actually takes place, but it is of the same order under nitrogen as in air. The disappearance of iodine is accompanied by the appearance of the characteristic pink colour of $\text{K}_2\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ in all cases, which remains for long periods even in the presence of diffused light if a few drops of dilute sulphuric acid have been previously added. Here the iodine evidently acts as a transport catalyst. So far as these experiments are concerned, there is thus no evidence for the existence of a peroxide of carbon in the presence of oxygen. The retardation may be simply due to the reaction

It is possible that oxygen may affect the other chain-carrier, Hg^+ , postulated by Roseveare, but this for the present must remain a matter of conjecture.

Failure to obtain reduction by adding HgCl_2 to the end solutions in the iodine-oxalate reaction may be accounted for by the fact that *two* chains depending upon the maintenance of a small stationary concentration of a common carrier would now have to be operative, namely, the Berthoud chain in the latter and the Cartledge chain. Conditions are thus present for a bifurcation of the energy-channels, which takes place apparently at the expense of the reaction

Finally it may be stated that experiments now in progress show that none of the other simple carboxylic acids reduces mercuric chloride in the presence of potassium permanganate at room temperature in a manner comparable with that of oxalic acid; the unique character of the latter in this respect appears to be due to the reactive half-ion.

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Received November 15, 1942.